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Securing and Managing DTNs

Wireless World Research Forum

Non-Terrestrial Networks

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This briefing is unclassified.

10.5281/zenodo.13937543

Use Case 1: Local Resource Preservation

Exemplar: A power-constrained wireless sensor network

- **Scheduled Node Transmissions**

- Radios powered as a function of time.
- Different nodes on at different times.

- **Assumptions**

- Power expenditures known.
- Power accumulation (solar) predictable.
- Resource (radio) management same.

- **Dynamic Topology**

- Connectivity changes over time.
- There might never be a single end-to-end path.
- Link up/down:
 - Predictable/Schedulable.
 - Communicable.

Assume a minimum local power to turn on radio.

Figure 1: Node Power Over Time

Figure 2: Topology over Time

Use Case 2: Adapting to External Conditions

Exemplar: On/Off Peak Cellular Usage

Costs are "high" during On-Peak.

- **"Costs" vary by node**

- Spatially distributed sensors.
- Connecting through cellular access.

- **Assumptions**

- Cost is measurable as data is charged by On/Off Peak data usage.
- Cost is scheduled and changes relatively slowly (twice a day).
- Cost magnitude may be significant given high overage fees.

- **Cost-Dynamic Topology**

- Physical topology unchanged
- Paths have different costs at different times.
- Can calculate when is best time to use a given end-to-end path (t1 or t3).
- Can calculate lowest cost path (store/forward) as combination t1 + t3.

Figure 3: Data Cost Over Time

Figure 4: Data Exchange Cost over Time

Figure 5: Data Cost using Storage

Use Case 3: Mobile Devices – with Predictable Connectivity

Exemplar: Networked LEO Constellation

- **LEO spacecraft links are short lived**

- Passes of several minutes each.
- Pass planning happens at ground terminals.
- Need to understand what node is over what terminal when.

- **Assumptions**

- Paths are predictable: motion and pointing can be understood in advance.
- Environmental knowledge is predictable: The environment being transmitted to and through can be well understood.

- **Dynamic Topology**

- Physical topology changes rapidly.
 - Internal network not so much (inter-satellite links)
 - Exit points (ground stations) very much.
- Satellite handoffs need to be planned (even in close advance).

Figure 6: Three Sequential Spacecraft

Figure 7: Spacecraft Ground Contacts Over Time

Figure 8: Constellation Topology Over Time

Solving Lunar Networking Technology Gaps

Engineering Open Standards for International Collaboration

- **Store and Forward Data Exchange**
 - **Do not** assume a path exists all at once.
 - **Do not** assume endpoints remember things for you.
 - **Do not** retransmit from the source. Inchworm through the network.
 - **Do** store data for milliseconds... or days.
 - **Do** carry all data and metadata in the same message.
- **End-to-end Security**
 - **Do not** rely solely on physical layer security.
 - **Do** secure different parts of a packet separately.
 - **Do** optimize for security at rest.
- **Autonomy as Network Management**
 - **Do not** assume an operator in the loop.
 - **Do** incorporate autonomy and automation. Operator “on” the loop.
 - **Do** push information proactively into the network.
 - **Do** be compatible with terrestrial management approaches.
- **Routing**
 - **Do** adjust to time-variant topologies.

Fig. 1. LunaNet Architecture

IETF Standards

APL is authoring networking standards and infusing them into devices

Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF)
Request for Comments: 9171
Category: Standards Track
ISSN: 2070-1721

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Bundle Protocol Version 7

Abstract

This document presents a specification for the Bundle Protocol, adapted from the experimental Bundle Protocol specification developed by the Delay-Tolerant Networking Research Group of the Internet Research Task Force and documented in RFC 5050.

Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF)
Request for Comments: 9172
Category: Standards Track
ISSN: 2070-1721

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January 2022

Bundle Protocol Security (BPsec)

Abstract

This document defines a security protocol providing data integrity and confidentiality services for the Bundle Protocol (BP).

Securing Delay-Tolerant Networks with BPsec
Dr Edward J. Birrane III
Sarah Heiner
Ken McKeever
WILEY

Per-Block Security Operations

BPsec security is applied to blocks, not bundles.

BPAs can secure different data differently.

Edward J. Birrane; Sarah Heiner; Ken McKeever, "The Design of the Bundle Protocol Security Extensions," in *Securing Delay-Tolerant Networks with BPsec*, Wiley, 2023, pp.71-92, doi: 10.1002/9781119823513.ch5.

Can fault autonomy be extended for network management?

What does a healthy intersection of these worlds look like?

- Express flight autonomy models using network management standards.
- Find ways to capture “domain-specific” languages where they exist.

Common command-based autonomy

A generalized autonomy model fits most fault autonomy systems

- Rule-based Systems

- Time and State
 - Time special case of state
- Special considerations
 - N of M evaluations
 - Maximum evaluations
 - Maximum fire counts

- Reason about instances not structures

- “If value of **X** at time **T...**”
- “Run a macro parameterized with a run-time variable”

- Cascading Rulesets

- If <bad condition> for 30 sec try thing 1.
- If <bad condition> for 60 sec try thing 2.

DTNMA Reference Model

Configuring the DTNMA Agent Application

- DTNMA Agent (DA)

- Application on a managed device
- Maintains a rules database
- Implements an autonomy engine
- Issues commands to co-resident managed applications.

- DTNMA Manager (DM)

- Manages the DA by configuring it
- Receives information from Das

- Modeling questions

- How do we represent the DA autonomy model?
- How to best transport configuration from a DM to a DA?

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